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“I Need to be Strong!”: The Lived Experiences of Davao Rescuers

Maejan Bilao, Rose Eden Dagohoy, Kriziella Alexandra Elman, Silvino Josol Jr.

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

Disasters occur during unanticipated events, in which immediate responses are needed under the process of rescue and relief operations. Rescuers play an important role during disasters and catastrophes, they ensure that public safety is prioritized. Rescuers deal with various rescue operations, and it was evident that they have faced challenging experiences going through emergencies and disaster responses. Although these duties are essential to the community, they are taxing on rescuers and increase their risk of trauma over time which may lead to poor performance at work, job dissatisfaction, and sleep deprivation. emergencies are unpredictable and cause destructive effects on our society, it has become an important research project in the field of crisis management for the development of scientific coping mechanisms and to improve rescuers' resilience. Psychological distress was experienced during disasters which affected the rescuers emotionally. Given that emergencies are unpredictable and cause destructive effects on our society, it has become an important research project in the field of crisis management for the development of scientific coping mechanisms and to improve rescuers' resilience.

Keywords: *rescuers, rescue operations, experiences, coping mechanisms*

Introduction

Disasters occur during unanticipated events, in which immediate responses are needed under the process of rescue and relief operations (Lucero & Froud, 2021). According to Keech et. al. (2019), rescuers play an important role during disasters and catastrophes, they ensure that public safety is prioritized. Rescuers deal with various rescue operations, and it was evident that they have faced challenging experiences going through emergencies and disaster responses. Although these duties are essential to the community, they are taxing on rescuers and increase their risk of trauma over time which may lead to poor performance at work, job dissatisfaction, and sleep deprivation (SAHMSA, 2018). As they deal with (possibly) traumatic mission events and ongoing work-related stress, rescuers are exposed to enduring emotional distress. Therefore, managing emotional distress appears to be crucial to sustaining the stress caused by work (Gartner, et al. 2018). Consequently, according to the Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration (2022), managing your emotions despite the stresses contributes to the resiliency of the rescuers during disaster situations.

In the United States of America, a study conducted by Parter (2018) revealed that it is important that the rescuer's experience is understood from their own perspective in order to provide them the sufficient supervision in accordance with their well-being, coping styles, stressors and specific traumas that they have had experienced. Specifically, another study by Leung (2022) mentioned that implementing post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) screenings are important for rescuers as they face different stressors as are continuously exposed to traumatic incidents. While Zola (2021), states that investing in connections that allow us to be vulnerable and lean on one another can ultimately increase our resilience. Furthermore, Lynn and Manager (2021), stated that behaviors correspond to continuous improvement and active intentional practice that can be developed across organizations.

In the Philippines, rescuers fearlessly engage in rescue operations amidst risky situations, they continue to strive and sustain the hardships faced which still paved the way for the emergence of healthcare needs among rescuers (Cañeda, Bejoc & Inabangan, 2018). Psychological distress was experienced during disasters which affected the rescuers emotionally (Corpuz et. al, 2019). Moreover, Castillo and Dela Cruz (2022) stated that serving as a rescuer may be a rewarding experience, but substantial responsibility comes with it, witnessing physical and psychological devastation which might greatly affect the rescuers physiologically and psychologically. A study conducted by Salutillo (2020) stated that extensive interpersonal relationships helped the rescuers improve their quality of life for it served as a self-care technique despite the stressors that are identified during disasters.

Recently, given that emergencies are unpredictable and cause destructive effects on our society, it has become an important research project in the field of crisis management for the development of scientific coping mechanisms and to improve rescuers' resilience (Shi, et al., 2018).The effectiveness of coping mechanisms for the rescuers is not thoroughly discussed and it is significant to determine if similar coping styles are used or may have changed accordingly (Bugtong, San Pedro & Caranto, 2019). Another study by Vagni et. al (2020) stated that the focus must involve support interventions in connection to their coping styles and as well as on understanding their experiences during traumatic events. Thus, the researchers identified the lack of research in the local setting related to the rescuer's experiences and their need for psychological assistance.

The objective of this research study is to unveil the lived experiences faced by the rescuers. To attain the goal of this study, the researchers formulated three research questions. First, the researchers would like to determine the challenging experiences of the rescuers. Additionally, the researchers would like to explore the coping mechanisms of the rescuers. Lastly, the researchers would like to identify the insights of the rescuers when faced with challenges.

This study will be beneficial to the rescuers, government, students, academe, and future researchers. This study will be valuable to the rescuers themselves because it will provide a ground for them so that they can be heard especially about their experiences and for people to understand their realities. Second, this will help the government to determine the perceptions of the rescuers wherein they could attend to and hear out the rescuers' concerns and requests. Moreover, this study will help the students to be aware and better comprehend the lived realities of rescuers which might greatly contribute to their existing knowledge in connection to the rescuers. Additionally, this study will be beneficial for the academe as it will serve as a reference for promoting sustainable responsibility to the students in their respective fields. As a molder, they can rely on the information and findings of the researchers. Furthermore, this research will give data for future researchers that are interested in the same study. They can use this research as a source of information that can as well contribute to their study. Lastly, the findings of this research can serve as a foundation that will also contribute to the body of knowledge by offering a far more in-depth understanding of the lived experiences of the rescuers.

The theories that will be used in this research study are the Resiliency Theory and the Planned Behavior Theory. According to the Resiliency Theory of O'Leary (1998), survival, recovery, and thriving are resilience concepts that define the stage at which a person may be during or after confronting tragedy. The concept of "thriving" refers to a person's capability to perform above and beyond his or her original level of functioning, as well as to adapt and function in the face of frequent stressful conditions. The study points to several things that make people resilient and effective. These variables include high self-esteem, tenacity, strong coping skills, a sense of coherence, self-efficacy, optimism, strong social resources, adaptability, taking risks, low fear of failure, determination, perseverance, and a high tolerance for ambiguity. In addition, Ledesma (2014) backed the Resiliency Theory and argued that the ability to recover from hardship, frustration, and tragedy is defined as resilience, and it is crucial for a leadership role. According to the literature, there is a direct relationship between the stress of the leader's job and their ability to retain resilience in the face of extended hardship. Thus, in the field of medicine, resilience theory was defined as the capability to recognize pain, acknowledge its purpose, and endure it for a period of time until things start to normalize (Flach, 1988; O'Leary & Ickovics, 1995). Also, the potential to bounce back from unfavorable life experiences and grow tougher while conquering them is broadly defined in the social sciences (Henderson & Milstein, 1996). Another theory that supports this study is the Planned Behavior Theory. According to Ajzen (1991), the planned behavior theory explains the emergence of behavior. Also, it explains how attitude is related to a plan and intention, which are then connected to factors such as the perspective with regards to behavior, subjective norms, and perceptions of perceived behavioral control which is directly tied to how behavior is produced. The applicability of The Planned Behavior theory in this research is anticipated to describe the factors that are beneficially related to the formation of correct responses in relation to standard procedures. According to Lamorte (2015), behavioral success is a function of both ability (behavioral control) and motivation (intention). Brookes (2021) added that the motivating variables that drive action are thought to be captured by intentions, which also serve as indicators of how much effort a person is prepared to put forth to carry out the behavior. In general, an activity should be more likely to be performed if there is a stronger intention to engage in it.

Methodology

Research Design

Qualitative phenomenological research design was utilized to understand the challenging experiences of the rescuers. This method determined and described the importance of phenomena by examining their perceptions and individual experiences (Alhazmi & Kaufmann, 2022). In addition, phenomenological research is a qualitative method that aims to comprehend and describe the fundamental essence of an event. The approach explores the everyday encounters of individuals without presuming anything about the phenomenon beforehand. In other words, phenomenological research examines lived events to acquire a greater understanding of how individuals interpret them. It seeks to deeply understand the phenomenon of rescuers by interpreting their subjective experiences, such as their feelings, perceptions, and beliefs as the researchers capture their lived experiences (Ho & Limpacher, 2022).

Participants

This study focuses mainly on the lived experiences of the rescuers. The participants were limited to fully-equipped and well-trained rescuers aged 18 and above who have the necessary identification documents, including IDs and certifications, and who have responded to any disasters and emergency responses during at least one year of their actual service in any accredited emergency station within Davao City. Hence, rescuers who have not experienced rescue operations for at least one year of service during disasters and emergencies (e.g. earthquakes, floods, fire etc.) were excluded from participating in this study. There were at least 7 participants selected through a non-probability purposive sampling. Furthermore, each participant was given a consent form prior to data collection, and they were given the option to withdraw from the study as long as they notify or contact the researchers by any convenient means at least one week before the interview, allowing the researchers to have enough time to find a suitable replacement. Their contribution was recognized, and they were given a token of appreciation for their time spent on this study.

Instrument

A research instrument is used as a tool to gather, measure, and analyze data. Hence, according to Dejonckheere and Vaughn (2019), the primary data source in qualitative research is the interview. In this qualitative study, researchers used an interview guide questionnaire to collect data regarding the lived experiences of the rescuers. The interview guide questionnaire that was utilized to

gather data is made by the researchers, which seek to find answers to their research questions. An in-depth interview in connection to the rescuer's experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights that were taken at least 30 minutes was done and recorded with the participants' proper consent; it was conducted through Zoom, MS Teams, or Facebook Messenger. The questions in the research underwent validation from experts as well as validation.

Procedure

This research undergoes a procedure that guided the researchers in conducting research. This phase contains the procedures that were followed in obtaining the qualitative data.

Permission from the Research Coordinator and Dean to Conduct the Study. The researchers addressed an approval letter to the University of Mindanao-College of Arts and Science Education dean and to the research coordinator of the department to conduct the study at the university. Following the approval, the researchers started the study which was evaluated accordingly by the research adviser and panel as well as the questionnaires that were used for the interview. In accordance with the comments and suggestions given by the evaluators, the researchers continued revising the study.

Permission from the Participants to Conduct the Study. Humbly, by reading the informed consent, the researchers asked the participants to participate in the study. The researchers ensured that the participant will be given the freedom to participate in the said research and withdraw their participation at any time they would want to. Thus, the findings of this study would remain anonymous and confidential.

Conducting the Interview. The researchers contacted the participants to ask for their available time to conduct the interview. Before the interview, the content of the consent form was explained to participants, and they were encouraged to ask questions in case there were things that were unclear to them. In this way, the participants will not be confused about what the research is all about and as well as its flow. At this phase, the interviewer asked the participants open-ended questions to converse and collect elicited data about a subject. This interview took at least 30 minutes of the participant's time. The participants were assured of the confidentiality of the information they have given. The interviews were recorded and kept properly by the researchers.

Encoding and Analysis of Data. The data were recorded, appraised, and measured by utilizing thematic analysis. The thematic analysis was done by the assigned analyst, who pulled out the themes to answer specific research questions and evaluate outcomes regarding the lived experiences of the rescuers.

Generating Results. The researchers made generalizations based on the findings of the study. Recommendations are as well cited.

Data Analysis

In extracting, organizing, and evaluating narrative data sets, thematic analysis was applied. Thematic analysis is an approach for evaluating qualitative data that involves examining a dataset to locate, interpret, and present repeating patterns (Kiger & Varpio, 2020). The assigned analyst had done the thematic analysis. Hence, the following steps will be pursued.

Learn the Data. Transcribe the data if it is in the form of audio files. Actively observe the themes and patterns that emerge throughout the transcripts and the data collection.

Practice Initial Coding. Create an initial set of codes based on the data's meanings and patterns. Re-evaluate the data, locate any noteworthy passages, and assign the proper codes to them. The same code should be used for all passages that convey the same message.

Group Codes into Themes. Organize all of the passages that are related to a particular code and categorize them into potential themes and sub-themes to highlight the relevant patterns in the data set.

Themes Finalization. Verify that each of the formulated themes is supported by sufficient data by reviewing and revising it. Examine related ideas and eliminate themes with insufficient supporting evidence. Start outlining how these themes can be formed into a narrative.

Formulating and Communicating the Narrative. As the last step in presenting your data narrative, composing the narrative and communicating its validity to the audience are important. The coherence between the formulated themes and the relevant supporting data should be observed in a logical manner. The narrative should include more than just a description of the data. It should also include the researchers' own interpretation and justification for the presented claims.

Ethical Considerations

In the conduct of the study, ethical considerations are observed. The researchers explain the nature of the research and the extent of their involvement in the study.

Informed Consent. Permission is always the top concern of the researchers before they go through interviews, it is part of the procedure by which the participants can voluntarily provide their willingness to participate in the study after knowing and understanding all relevant research information. Thus, in this research study, after explaining the procedure that the participants undergo, they will be given a prior consent form that would show that they are willing to be a participant in this study. Also, the researchers ensure that the participants have the right to decline, withdraw, and raise questions whenever they desire to.

Confidentiality. The researchers respected the participants' decisions to hide their true identities; thus, pseudonyms were provided. Their anonymity and any information obtained are highly respected and secured from unauthorized access, disclosure, modification, loss, and theft. They are kept private and confidential. After the research, the data must be securely archived or deleted in the most appropriate way that prevents the information from being reconstructed. Any information leaked will be held accountable to the researchers, so utmost data protection would always be observed.

Respect for Person. It is the recognition of the participants as autonomous, unique, and free individuals. The researchers will also acknowledge that each participant has the right and authority to make their own choices. This premise also supports the principle of obtaining informed consent before conducting the research.

Justice. This speaks to the fair distribution of advantages and the fact that no participants are being taken advantage of. In essence, the researchers will make sure that the sampling technique used is ethical and doesn't harm the participants.

Results and Discussion

This section thoroughly discuss the results of the gathered data that went through thematic analysis, which is an approach for evaluating qualitative data that involves examining a dataset to locate, interpret, and present repeating patterns (Kiger & Varpio, 2020).

The data gathered from the participants were analyzed using thematic analysis. This data analysis aims to accurately understand and describe the lived experiences of Davao rescuers. The thematic analysis consists of five steps, wherein each step is designed to ensure thorough analysis. The research on the lived experiences of Davao rescuers came up with nine themes such as *Risky and Dangerous Job, Lack of Manpower and resources, Experienced Harassment and Being Mocked, Staying Positive, Having Support System, Having Recreational Activities, Being a Rescuer is Not an Easy Task, Be Passionate, and Equipt Oneself with Knowledge and Skills*.

The Challenges and Struggles faced by the Davao Rescuers

Risky and Dangerous Job. Risky and dangerous job often involve harm, injury and might cost someone's life. Rescuers are one of the jobs that are relatively very dangerous.

Participant 1 described the challenges/struggles faced during rescues, there was a time when they were trapped and were almost swept away.

"naanod mi kay kusog kaayong current so mao tong struggle nako didto sa lasang alambri nalang nag kuan samo ug katong lubi." (We were swept away by the strong current. That was the struggle I experienced in Lasang, and it was only the wire and the coconut tree that saved us.) -P1

Similarly, Participant 2 reported that challenges/struggles are experienced when people become way too impatient, and people would threaten them which leads to risks on their part as well. Also, Participant 2 described how difficult it is when doing operations during a flood because the current is most of the time—strong but they still needed to risk their lives just to save and rescue people.

"Naa.ahh ang pinakalisod namo na operation...is kanang baha. samtang naga rescue mi kay ang amoa man gung ginasulod usahay kusog na kaayo ang current labi na kining mga uban tao, gahi kaayo manggawas ingnan nimog gawas namo sa mubo pa ang tubig, dili manggawas kay ang tubag "anad nami" (Our most difficult operation was during a flood. While we were rescuing people, the current would sometimes become very strong, especially some people who were hesitant to come out and kept saying, "we are used to this.") -P2

Moreover, Participant 3 stated that shooting incidents are often very risky especially when the police officers are not yet present on the scene upon their arrival, because their safety is at risk which can be very dangerous on their part as well.

"Daghan.. daghan.. like kaning kuan... .ahhh... shooting incident for example... .ang shooting incident man gud, wata kabalo ang gipatay ba ron naa pa diha, syempre as a first responder...ahh ang pinaka work jud namo is safety first jud namo.

..kasagaran gyud na risky sa amoa kana jung mga..kanang mga kuan trauma case jud kanang gi dunggab ba ron, gi pusil ba ron, gi luba ba ron, ingana gud, mao na nga.. isa na sa pinaka delikado sa amoa..walay mag una sa mga authority para sa among safetyess." (There are many struggles, such as the shooting incident, for example. When a shooting incident happens, we don't know who has been killed or injured, so as first responders, our top priority is our safety. It is very risky for us, especially when we encounter trauma cases like those who have been stabbed, shot, or beaten. This is why it is one of the most dangerous things for us, there are no authorities present to ensure our safety.)- P3

Participant 6 stated that vehicular accidents, bystanders, and flooding are the most common hazards and risks in times of emergency. Bystanders would often try offering help but would just make things risky for everyone, and floods cause the risk of drowning, which is why it is important to know the necessary precautions to avoid such risks.

"Daghan, naa man gyud na siya, sa in times of emergency naa gyud na, mga hazard and risks..usually...ahhh..ang hazard ang risk, for example..VA, VA stands for vehicular accident then, so daghan gyug mga hazards and risks, dira number one kanang mga bystanders, bystanders..so dili gyud na malikayan na gusto nila ba na mapadali gani ang pagtabang sailang..sailang kuan..sailang

tagtungod nila..sailahang patient. Number two, kanang sa flood, ahh 2017, sa may jade valley, bahaonon jud na siya sa jade valley, kana..kanang mga hazards and risks especially kanang mo..kaning..sa flood..kana dili gyud malikayan naay mga..ahhh..prone pud na siyag ga drowning diha, ahh..pagkakamali ra nimo diha, masipyat ka pwede jud nimong ikamatay pud.” (There are really many times like in times of emergency, there are many hazards and risks that need to be considered, such as vehicular accidents (VA) and other dangers. Among the top hazards are bystanders who often want to help but can create additional risks for patients and emergency responders. Another significant hazard is flooding, as seen in 2017 in Jade Valley, where the risk of drowning was high, and a single mistake could have led to death, it is important to be aware of such hazards and to take all necessary precautions to prevent accidents and ensure the safety of everyone involved.) -P6

Furthermore, Participant 7 described that there are a lot of dangers in doing rescue operations such as sudden falls or slides when rescuing on riverbanks or in the mountains, having injuries from carrying a patient, and getting infected from the patient's illness which makes their lives at risk.

“bale unang danger naki na mahatag kanang, naa miy usahay marescue sa pampang, kanang bukid- bukid. So, anytime pwede maslide, pwede mi matagak. Next, kanang pag karga sa pasyente medyo sa pag tan-aw sa uban tao is easy ra sya kay karga-karga lang. However, naa tay mga times ana is mali lang atong pagkarga masakit atong likod madaot ang atong likod. So, kuan gyud na sya ma.. naa jud nay dakong effect sa atong lawas. Lastly, murag mao ni ang pinaka danger sa tanang danger pwede mi.. pwede mi as a rescuer madali mi matakdan as a rescuers sa mga sakit sa pasyente.” (The first danger is when we need to perform a rescue on the riverbank or in the mountains. We can slide or fall anytime. Next, carrying the patient may look easy to others, but there are times when we lift them improperly and it can cause back pain or injury. It is really a challenge and it can have a big impact on our body. Lastly, the most dangerous thing among all the dangers is getting infected by the patient's illness. As rescuers, we are always at risk of contracting the patient's illness.) -P7

These are consistent with the study conducted by Cañeda, Bejoc, and Inabangan (2018) which stated that rescuers fearlessly engage in rescue operations amidst risky situations. Rescuers displayed resilience all throughout risky and dangerous operations, wherein they emphasized that being a rescuer it is important to strive and sustain different hardships to save lives. Moreover, another study by Castillo and Dela Cruz (2022) described that being a rescuer comes with substantial responsibility as they continue to witness different devastation. Risky and dangerous jobs can negatively affect an employee's performance and well-being. According to SAHMSA (2018), risky jobs can have possible effects such as having a higher risk for post-traumatic stress disorder(PTSD), stress, depression, and other behavioral health concerns, this can then lead to dissatisfaction and poor performance at work.

Lack of manpower and resources. Lack of manpower and resources can lead to compromised output and delays might as well occur. Problems arise as these factors are continuously not given the proper solution.

Participant 3 reported the lack of manpower and resources and expressed how hard it is to manage the team since most of the members are quite young and are only volunteers.

“isa ka problem pud namo diri is kining syempre dili man nato ma blame ang mga bata kay..mga volunteer man..from the word volunteer itself man gud..tawag ani...di nimo siya mapugos na mukuan diri..mu stay diri or unsa kay manginabuhi pud na sila gud unlike anang mga tambay, kana..pwede sad tambay diri pero ang uban man gud na...ahhh member diri kasagaran studyante so pag naa mi mga dagan...mga operation, kulang mig tao, dili nimo sila basta basta ma hulbot, mao pud nay isa ka kuan namo...isa ka trials namo diri.” (We cannot blame them because they are all just volunteers. From the word volunteer itself, you can't force someone to stay here or to live here because they have other things going on in their lives. Some people may choose to just hang around, but most of the members here are students, and when there is an event or operation, and we do not have enough people, we cannot just force them to come. That is one of the trials we face here.) -P3

Participant 5 stated how lacking their resources can be especially financially, given that they are part of a non-government organization, they needed to fund their operations to finance whatever needs are present. Due to a lack of resources, there are times that it is impossible to respond since there are no vehicles that can be used as transportation.

“ang isa sa among challenges is ang...ahh...financial, ahh... especially non-government organization me so, wala mi connection between barangays or any nga... sa government para mag finance sa among needs, so kami as a group kami lang naga ambag-ambag, kami naga ahh... kami naga buhi sa among grupo, so isa na siya sa among challenges, and then, sometimes miscommunication, especially if in an operation ahh... sa locations or ahh... asa nga, kanang ahhm... mag-miscommunicate gani ma'am, kuntahay ahhm... location naa mi ano, naa mi ahh... call, naa mi emergency call sa isa ka remote nga area, for example diria sa toril ahh.. Uhh... ano sa ahh... upland area, so didto sa upland area magli- pag-ma abot me didto sa scenario mag lisod namig communicate gikan didto sa area pabalik sa amoang base station due to, sa... ahh- sa signals sa radio and isa na sa among struggles and then, also ang isa pud namo sa struggles is ang ahh... sa among group is ang transport, kay sometimes... mag respond me og call nga wala mi enough nga resources or vehicle, mao na ang isa namong challenges and struggles nga among ma face.”(one of our challenges is... the financial... especially we are a non-government organization so... we do not have connections between barangays or among any... in the government to finance our needs, so we, as a group give small amounts each... to make our group functional... that is why it is also a challenge for us... and then.. sometimes miscommunication... especially about locations... like there are possibilities to

miscommunicate... we have a call... an emergency call from a remote area... when we get there in the scenario... we're having a difficult time communicating from that remote area to our base due to... our radio signals... also one of our struggles is how to transport... because sometimes when we respond to a call... we don't have any enough resources or vehicles... so that's one of the struggles we faced.) -P5

These results are in line with the study of Lucero and Froud (2021), in which it was mentioned that unanticipated events often occur in which immediate responses are needed, in which lack of manpower and resources can be a big factor that might greatly impact the success rate of the rescue operation. Keech et. al. (2019) also stated that rescuers play an important role during disasters and catastrophes. This implies that manpower is very vital to conduct successful rescue operations, their lack of manpower greatly causes an impact when emergencies tend to arise. Another study by Anderson (2022) stated that lack of manpower especially when it comes to rescue and public safety concerns often take place due to difficulty in recruiting the workforce given that interests in technology are more evident than working in emergency departments, burnout can also be a factor for employees leaving their posts. It was implied that recruitment is quite a challenge when looking for another rescuer. On the other hand, burnout due to being short-handed and being required to work extra hours are the reasons for other employees to leave their departments which leads to a further shortage of manpower. Furthermore, proper rescue equipment is needed for prompt response which makes the rescue operations efficient and easier, deficiency in different equipment will lead to poor and failed rescue operations (Ojha & Khatiwada, 2023).

Experienced harassment and being mocked. Harassment and mockery can greatly affect the performance of a certain person. It can negatively change one's perspective and motivation on doing one's work.

Participant 2 described how people often say hurtful and demotivating words. There are instances where people would intend to physically harm the rescuers and would otherwise complain instead of thanking them.

"for how many times nana nahitabo samoa, labi na sakoa, ingnon kag "dugaya ninyo sir uy"...niya "sayang lang ang gisweldo sainyo sa bara...— gobyerno", daghan..daghan nana nahitabo unya usahay i-harass pajud ka sa tag tungod sa pasyente, ingon ana ba..ingana na mga pangitabo..daghan na kaayo halos..mga halos makigsumbagay samoa. Usahay kasab-an mi, so ako pud usahay mutubag pud ko" (This has happened to me and others on the rescue team. It is hurtful and demotivating when we are told things like "you are taking too long" or "you are just wasting the salary given by the government." Sometimes, we also face harassment from patients or their families. There had been a lot of instances when they would intend to punch us, and we would be scolded. That's why I would sometimes talk to them.) -P2

Participant 6 expressed that criticisms from other organizations had been a struggle, though given that they have the same goal, it cannot be eliminated and it significantly affects their group because those critiques cannot be justified knowing that their intention is to help throughout.

"Actually, for the past 8 years no, sa...volunteer organization pinaka ahh most challenged or struggle siguro ahh kanang mga criticism bitaw sa uban, ubang organization so.. dili man jud siya malikayan no na..naa gyud na siyay kanang competition although same raman mog goal na mutabang sa community, pero nganong naa may uban na mo criticize sainyohang grupo, so mga ingon ana..criticism.. tanang mga comment..negative comment about sainyong grupo, so di na nimo siya malikayan..so for me mao na ang struggle.." (In the past eight years, our volunteer organization has faced some of the most challenging and persistent criticism from others, even from other organizations. Unfortunately, such criticism cannot be entirely avoided, given the competitive landscape in which we operate, although our common goal remains the same which is helping the community. Nonetheless, it is disheartening to receive negative comments and unjustified critiques about our group. This has been a significant struggle for us and one that we continue to address.) -P6

Moreover, Participant 6 also stated that criticisms are the last things that they needed as a group, others should collaborate with solidarity knowing that their intentions are to help during operations because criticisms would just affect each organization and it will not promote the common good among everyone.

"Siguro kaning kuan.aahh. times sa pag response, ahh kana mao gyud na kanang criticism jud ma'am, kaning usually dapat jud sa isa ka organization or sa other organization mag tinabangay, unity, camaraderie man gyud, for me, para mahimong successful ang operation or ang emergency na inyong gi response, so for me mao na ang kuan... criticism, makawala man gud na siyag gana...sa response..dapat gani mag tinabangay dili Ninyo idown ang isa't isa, ana." (Perhaps during times of response, criticism is the last thing we need. As a rule, organizations should collaborate, promoting unity and camaraderie, in order to ensure the success of operations and emergency responses. Criticism only demotivates and hinders the response process. Instead, it is important for organizations to work together and support each other, rather than bring each other down.) -P6

Experiencing harassment and being mocked in a workplace or while doing one's job can greatly disrupt one's focus and functioning. According to Francik et. al (2020), any form of harassment mostly psychological violence can affect a person's functioning specifically mental, physical, and social. The harassment and mockery encountered can greatly affect a person and might become demotivating on their part. On the other hand, it was stated by Stringer (2021) that constructive criticisms are necessary to re-evaluate performance and to continuously improve on future assignments. Criticisms are often constructive but taken negatively, but it will always be there to

help people improve, thus, it is best to think of the importance of support within the workplace and across organizations instead of criticizing and focusing on the negative performance of different people and organizations.

The Coping Mechanisms of the Davao Rescuers while facing challenging experiences

Staying Positive. Maintaining a positive mindset and attitude in challenging situations must often be considered to properly set a goal despite hardships. It can enhance the way of seeing things and coping with disaster situations.

Participant 1 emphasized the importance of trust and positivity in assisting those affected by disasters. Participant 1 believed that having a positive attitude could significantly contribute to helping people in need.

“Ahhm ano.. para sa akua lang po, think positive lang po ug ano.. naay trust sa kauban ug ang amoa gyung... goal nga matabangan ang mga tao nga nasalanta didto.” (For me, it is important to think positively and to have trust in others, and our goal is to help the people who were affected by the disaster.) -P1

On the other hand, Participant 2 took a more relaxed approach to handling criticism and focused on aiding others.

“Ahh. Among ginahimo is kuan lang..ahhh..palapos nalang pud namo sa pikas dalunggan. Ahh.. “ug ikaw di pakuha” ana “naa ra saimoha di mana problema namo” so para maka move on mi sa mga ingon ana istoryahan rapud namog balik pagka human ana diritso nami sa next goal napud namo na ginahimo.” (Our approach is just casual... we'll just let it pass through our ear. And we would tell them “if you don't want to be rescued, it is not our problem anymore”, so to move on, we will just talk about those things and then we will go straight to our next goal.) -P2

Participants 3 and 4 stressed the significance of staying calm and focused to avoid confusion and provide efficient assistance.

“Kuan, ang isa diha na ginabuhay nako kay..kalma...ahhh focus..kalma because once man gud maratol ka..maratol ang tanan..syempre ikaw as a team leader dapat ipakita nimo sa mga tao nimo nga di ka dapat maratol. Kay once maratol ka, maratol pud sila. Tapos pud focus, dapat focus ka saimong gitrabaho diha, ug saimong gitrabaho para..kay ang goal nimo is to save lives, mao na focus ka, mao na akong main goal na dapat kung naa ka sa area, kalma the focus para ma reach nimo imong aim, ma..ma reach nimo imong aim as a first aider or as a first responder nga mutabang ka ana to save lives.” (One of the things I do is to keep calm and focused. It is important not to panic because once you do, everyone else will as well. As a team leader, it is important to show your team that you are in control and not in panic. You need to stay focused on your work and your goal, which is to save lives. That is why I always make sure to stay calm and focused so that I can achieve my aim as a first aider or first responder and help save lives.) -P3

Participant 4 also mentioned the same coping mechanism as a rescuer:

“Ahh...sa akua is kuan jud focus lang, focus ka tapos presence of mind na dili ka mawala sa—kanang, kuan ba dili ka matanga, labi nag naa naka sa area nimo so di ka makita nimong mga pasyente nimo dapat di jud mawala sa focus.” (Ahh... for me is to just focus... and not lose my presence of mind... so that you are not left dumbfounded whenever you are in the area seeing your patients... you should not lose focus.) -P4

Participant 6 highlighted using diversionary strategies and constructive feedback to overcome obstacles and manage stress.

“Strategies..para katong...ahhh..ma overcome gihapon...kato, kato akong giingon ganiha na gina divert namo among...amoang..syempre sa isa ka organization man gud naa gyud na siyay..wala man gyuy perfect diba na org naa jud na siyay mga stress...stress sa grupo..di magkasinabtanay, stress pa sa ubang grupo napud..mga comment, mga criticism.....amoa lang ano..ahhh.. take back it..na..imbes pa..if..kuntahay dira pud mi ga cope..kanang refresher course namo, kinahanglan nimo mag refresh man gud no Mao na..diha namo gina...gina divert among ano..kanang sa mga stress..kana.” (The strategies to overcome the challenges that we have encountered are as mentioned earlier, we divert our attention to our organization. There is no perfect organization, and some groups experience stress and misunderstandings. There may be comments or criticisms, but we take them constructively. Instead of getting stressed, we divert our focus to our refresher courses. This is how we divert our attention from stress.) -P6

At the same time, Participant 7 emphasized the importance of a positive mindset as the foundation for effective coping techniques and resilience.

“Strategies?...wala man koy medyo, kana lang to sya ma'am kailangan gyud nimo ikuan.. ang trabaho as a positive kay kung dili biskan naa ka atong coping mechanism nimo dili na sya makuan as a coping mechanism, kung dili positive ang imong tan-aw sa mga kuan. So, mao nang first, first na... ginahimo ginahuna huna jud nako positive para along the run sa kinabuhay positive gihapon sya, bahala ug unsa sya kalisud, tapos dina na magsunod ang ginatawag nato na coping mechanism para magpadayon... og magpadayon gihapon bisan lisud na ang trabaho.” (Strategies?...I don't really have any, it's just that you really need to have a positive outlook...because if you don't have any coping mechanism, it won't be effective as a coping mechanism if you don't see it positively. So, that's the first thing, I always think positive, so that in the long run, it will still be positive no matter how difficult it is. Then, the next step is to follow what we call coping mechanisms to continue...and still continue even if the job is hard.) -P7

These findings are consistent with a study by Pruthi, Arora and Allen (2022) on positive thinking, which explains that positive thinking does not involve ignoring the challenges in life. Instead, it involves addressing negativity constructively and optimistically and

expecting positive outcomes rather than dwelling on negative possibilities. Regularly engaging in positive thinking makes you better equipped to handle everyday stress constructively. Over time, you may criticize yourself less, become more accepting of yourself, and develop a more unbiased view of the world around you. Moreover, according to the Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration (2022), managing your emotions despite the stresses contributes to the resiliency of the rescuers during disaster situations. It allows them to see the whole picture clearly, improve self-awareness, and open a range of choices to solve problems, so they can perform at their best and cope with negativities.

This is inclined in the development of positive psychology which focused on the positive depiction of the experiences of humans that have increased one's quality of life by promoting qualities that can positively impact psychological well-being (Seligman and Csikszentmihalyi, 2000; Sinval et. al., 2018). Under the concept of positive psychology lies the perspective of work engagement that is focused on the positive attributes of a behavior such as when workers dedicate themselves to their work it can be seen as a form of motivating situation (Saks, 2006; Zhu & Song, 2022). Lastly, according to O'Leary (1998), the concept of thriving which was displayed when they continued to stay positive despite the situation have encountered. The capability to perform and adapt to function despite stressful conditions was what resiliency theory emphasized.

Having Support System. Emphasizing the importance of networks of support and collaborative problem-solving in fostering resilience are very significant. This helps in restoring mental and physical well-being amidst stressful situations.

Participant 2 emphasizes the importance of sharing challenges and setbacks with coworkers to avoid being slowed down by them.

"Dugay ana among mag istoryahanay mi, gina istoryahan namo ang mga nahitabo, pagkahuman ana move on..move on para, dili mi ingon nga kanang..ahh..mao rani hinungdan para maka undang sakoa, amoa jud na siyang i..amoa jud na siyang lingkuran, istoryahan." (What I do is I just tell myself to let go of my worries and move on. We take some time to talk about what happened and then we move on. We don't dwell on the past or let it stop us from doing our duty. We serve our community, and we do our best to help people in need. We talk about what we can do better next time so we can avoid similar situations.) -P2

Likewise, the coping strategy of Participant 5 includes conducting a post-emergency call review with his coworkers. This practice refreshes his knowledge and allows him to fill any memory gaps that may occur. Participant 5 and his team are committed to learning and growing from their experiences by continually seeking to enhance their performance and fill knowledge gaps.

"after sa among mga call or any emergency call kay kuan lang,, kumbaga post assessment lang sa mga, sa mga nahitabo sa... during operation, kuntahay ahh... ako naa koy lapses akoa tong i-ask sa akong kauban nga ahh... "badi unsaon gani to, nakalimot naman ko ani" so after ana, amoa nang gina refresh among knowledge, mao na siyang mahulog nga coping mechanism namo para lang, para lang ma storyahan namo ang mga nahitabo kaganiha, sometimes mag kinataw-anay pa mi kay naa mi mga lapses nga nabuhat... ahh..ah, so mao to siya ang coping mechanism namo as a rescuer." (after any emergency call, I do a post-assessment to refresh my knowledge of what happened during the operation. Sometimes I have lapses, and I ask my partner, "What happened? I forgot." That is when we refresh our knowledge, and that is our coping mechanism as rescuers.) -P5

These results align with the study of Zola (2021), which states that investing in connections that allow us to be vulnerable and lean on one another can ultimately increase our resilience. We can get through challenging times feeling cared for and less alone if we maintain helpful interactions with others. In addition, resilience may require time to develop, so individuals should not be discouraged if they continue to face difficulties in coping with challenging events. An important way to build resilience is to consider that it does not necessarily involve following a specific set of behaviors or actions and can significantly differ from one person to another. The key is to continue to concentrate on practicing these skills and embracing the common traits observed in resilient individuals. However, it is also essential to remember to build upon existing strengths (Cherry, 2022). Consequently, According to Rilveria (2018), social support (paghingi ng tulong) which refers to the support received from either friends or family and receiving support and care from professionals as well as advice are part of the human ability to determine or manage a difficulty encountered, for social support strengthens the well-being of an individual to better strive despite hardships. Overall, these behaviors correspond with the model of continuous improvement, an active, intentional practice that is ideally developed across an organization as a whole. (Lynn & Manager, 2021).

Having Recreational Activities. The rescuers in this study employ various coping mechanisms to manage the stress and demands of their profession. These strategies include engaging in recreational activities, such as enjoying coffee or pursuing personal hobbies, as well as redirecting their focus towards self-improvement through training and knowledge enhancement.

For Participant 5, savoring a cup of coffee serves as a means to unwind and replenish his energy levels after a demanding operation. This ritual brings him solace and relaxation, enabling him to recharge and restore his mental and physical well-being. Participant 5 also recognizes that coping techniques may vary among individuals, with some finding stress relief and emotional support through activities like smoking or engaging in other hobbies.

"Ang coping mechanism namo ginabuhat is syempre pag uli sa station or sa amoang base station is kape lang ahh... tabi kabuan sa among mga co-rescuers, and then syempre if ang uban nay mga bisyo mag sigarilyo then ang uban ahh... naga... naga depende na pero sa akoa personally po ma'am." (So, our coping mechanism is to have coffee when we return to the station or our base station, and we also lean on our co-rescuers for support. Some of them smoke, and others do other things.) -P5

Meanwhile, Participant 6 describes a coping strategy that involves redirecting his focus away from stress and towards self-improvement. This cognitive shift allows him to immerse himself in activities that promote personal growth and professional development, creating a positive outlet for stress and anxiety

“Akong coping mechanism para..para sa kuan..para ma overcome nimo ang kuan.. actually, so far, wala man, ang coping mechanism ra nako para usahay, ma stress ta sa atong trabaho as a rescuer, kana lang..murag ilibang lang nimo imong sarili..kanang...murag...dili nimo siya huna hunaon ba.sa....amoa pud ing ana imbes istress nimo ang isa ka butang..inyo nalang siyang itraining, mag refresh mo..mag refresh mo sainyong mga natun- an...ana murag dagdag knowledge nalang pud...ana.” (So far I actually do not have a specific way to deal with facing challenges as a rescuer, but when I get stressed at work as a rescuer, I distract myself by focusing on training and refreshing my knowledge. This helps me avoid stressing over something and turn it into an opportunity to gain more knowledge.) -P6

These findings align with a study by The View Point Center (2021), which demonstrates that recreational activities relieve stress and have been shown to alleviate anxiety and depression. In these cases, allowing one's mind to clear and remain uncluttered may initially seem counterintuitive, but it can have both physical and emotional calming effects. With practice, the benefits include long-term stress relief and a reduction in stress reactivity, among other positive outcomes. Furthermore, having recreational activities helps to feel relaxed, it also refers to the involvement of different activities that would lessen the current baggage of stress and temporarily helps a person from thinking of the problem at hand (Rilvera, 2018; Fermin et. al, 2022). Regardless of the chosen approach, the underlying idea is that relaxation and leisure time are not luxuries but essential components for living a healthy and less stressful life (Scott, 2020). The significance of recreation is often overlooked, but it should be considered a necessity rather than a luxury. Leisure activities have therapeutic benefits for the mind, body, and soul, and they are important in various domains of life, including cognitive, affective, social, physical, and spiritual aspects (Shamsuddin, 2022).

The Insights and Recommendations of the Davao Rescuers when faced with Challenges

Being a Rescuer is Not an Easy Task. Being a rescuer is not an easy task as it involves the life of different people that needs help. It requires tremendous mental and physical strength.

Participant 1 revealed that it is difficult to be a rescuer. For participant 1, to be able to do the work well you need to put God first and strong communication with your team to succeed.

“ahh... for me maam is ano makisama,makisama ug ano di jud na mawala ang put God first diha jud na so kanang maminaw sa isat isa kakauban para mag communicate mo na as a rescuer naa namoy salbahon nga patient.” (For me, ma'am, it is all about teamwork, cooperation, and keeping God as our top priority. It is essential to listen to each other and communicate effectively, especially when we are rescuing a patient.) -P1

Similarly, participant 6 stated that being a rescuer is not an easy task he mentioned questioning your self-worth and receiving negative feedback from others. However, it is not important to stick with negativity, always remember the work you do is valuable for others.

“Ahh..dili siya lalim..dili siya lalim na ma encounter..kay maka affect jud siya personally saimoha, murag usahay maka..maka feel ka ba na worth it ba ka..worth it baka na individual as a rescuer..ana ahh. Murag ma compare nimo imong sarili sa uban, na ingana ingana, pero, mao na ug dili huna hunaon ang negative effects gikan sa laing tao.” (Being a rescuer is not an easy task, and the experiences encountered can have a personal impact on you. At times, you may question your own worth as a rescuer and compare yourself to others. However, it is important to not dwell on any negative effects from others and instead focus on taking care of yourself emotionally and seeking support when needed. Remember that the work you do as a rescuer is valuable and necessary, and you are making a difference in the lives of people.) -P6

The participants revealed that being a rescuer is a difficult job and not an easy task. Participant 1 stated that communication plays a significant role as well as faith. While Participant 6 stated that it affects oneself and often leads to questioning one's capability, it is important to focus on self-care emotionally and as well as seeking support all throughout. Disaster emergency rescuers run the danger of suffering from negative psychological effects. According to Mao et. al (2018), as rescuers are deployed to sites that have experienced disasters, rescuers tend to suffer anxiety and depression and become more susceptible emotionally and mentally. Some, meanwhile, are reportedly resilient and shielded from unfavorable effects. As they experience strong negative emotions such as worrying and fear, it reflects on their physical and mental well-being, and economic situations also become a factor in rescuer's stressors, such as in terms of decreased wages while having the fear of losing their job (Giorgi et al., 2015; Mucci et al., 2016; Gartner et. al, 2018). Additionally, it was determined that there were differences in the spiritual quality of life as a coping mechanism among rescuers that can be related to years of experience, but occupational hardiness is a factor that can greatly affect the spiritual quality of life among rescuers (Assaf & Alsadi, 2022).

Be Passionate. They are committed to rescuing lives in even the most difficult situations because of their unwavering passion. Rescuers continue to do what needs to be done because they know how important their role can be.

Participant 2 stated that in facing the challenges having a goal which is to help those in need to be rescued can make a difference.

“Ang tumong namo..labi na sakoa ang akong tumong is ang pagtabang sa nanginahanglanug kaluwasan sa kalag sa tao. Sa gamay na pamaagi na makatabang mi, mao na ang importante para sa akoo.” (Our goal, especially mine, is to help those who need to be rescued and save lives. Even in small ways, we can make a difference, and that is important to me.) -P2

Participant 4 also shared his insights as a rescuer that you need to be passionate about your work. You must work with heart and help others wholeheartedly.

“Ako kay, sa akong ka-agi..nako... akoo, dili man jud ko kanang medical inclined pero naabot ko ani na trabaho, siguro, in God's will, na... naabot ko ani para makatabang siguro jud sa katawhan or sa akoo pud is... kanang, nisulod ko ani is dili lang, para makatabang sa lahi nga tao pud, makatabang pud sa sarili na pamilya mao nang, kung nisulod ko ani dapat buhaton jud nakong part na makatabang, dili lang kay sa kanang ing ani na nisulod ka ani kay tungod sa ana... uniform tungod lang sa ing ani iyang.. imohang rango d-dili tungod sa ing ana dapat tungod sa imohang kasing-kasing na makatabang sa laing tao or sa imong pamilya or sa imong mga relatives.”(For me...based on my experience...I am not really medically inclined... but I am in this field... maybe it was the will of the Lord to be here... and to help others... and for me is to not just help other people but also for myself and family...That is why when I decided to enter this kind of field... I should do my part to help...I am here not because of the uniform...the rank... not like that... but because you whole-heartedly wanted to help others or for your family and relatives.) -P4

The two participants stated that to be able to do well in their job being passionate is a must. Participant 2 has an unwavering dedication to his job shows through as he refuses to be discouraged by the difficulty of the task at hand and insists on enlisting the help of coworkers at the nearby hospital to assure their patient's survival. While Participant 4 faces dangerous conditions and difficult obstacles. Brookes (2021) stated that the motivating variables that drive action are thought to be captured by intentions, which also serve as indicators of how much effort a person is prepared to put forth to carry out the behavior. In general, an activity should be more likely to be performed if there is a stronger intention to engage in it. Consequently, passion at work leads to achieving work-related goals, it influences not just their career alone but as well as their well-being as they continuously become committed (Jung & Sohn, 2022). Work passion reinforces productive effects in an employee and leads to lifelong motivation to strive.

Equip oneself With Knowledge and Skill. The value of improving one's knowledge and abilities are done in order to ensure that they are fully equipped when performing their job. Every rescue operation involves different cases which needs to be handled accordingly.

Participant 5 mentioned that the challenges are not just challenges for them, challenges help to improve the rescuers' growth and consider such factors to do well in the future.

“So... kani siya nga mga kalisod nga among ma agian ma'am is syempre challenges jud ni siya, as- sa imoha pang question, so challenge siya para sa amoa pero at the same time isa pud siya sa makatabang sa amoa, para sa among growth as a rescuer, makadag-makadagdag sa among experience, makadagdag sa among knowledge and then, ahh... ano pud isa pud siya sa mga factors nga...magamit namo during ahh... for the next operation.”(So... the difficulties that we encounter, ma'am, are of course challenges for us. As to your question, it is a challenge for us, but at the same time, it also helps us, for our growth as rescuers. It adds to our experience, adds to our knowledge, and also, it is one of the factors that we can use for the next operation.) -P5

Consequently, Participant 6 stated that avoiding challenges would not help you to improve. Evaluating yourself and identifying the areas you are lacking will help you to improve yourself and your role in work.

“For me...kuan siya...na mga challenge, kani na mga challenge man kay kung di pud ka kaagi ug kalisod, dili ka maka agi ug mga...mga negative na..unsa bay anything na negative diha, dili pud ka magimprove, ahhh.. thankful pud mi, kanang mga challenge or struggle..sa grupo.ahhh..thankful mi kay kana siya nahimo na siyang outcome para mag improve me, i-evaluate namo among sarili..kung asa mi nagkulang, unsa ang need namo na i- improve para mahimong better..sa isa ka society as a volunteer rescue..rescuer.” (For me, these challenges are necessary because without going through difficulties, you can't avoid negative things. If you do not face challenges, you would not be able to improve. We are also thankful for the challenges or struggles within the group because they serve as an outcome that helps us improve. We evaluate ourselves to identify areas where we are lacking and need improvement to become better rescuers within the volunteer rescue society.)-P6

The participants revealed learning from previous experiences and how growth can be essential in constantly developing one's skills. Participant 6 stated that improvement is vital. While Participant 5 stated that experiences are what make them learn continuously as it adds knowledge. The rescuers exhibit a broad range of expertise and abilities necessary for their position, they have the expertise in emergency response techniques and have the aptitude to recognize and manage life-or-death emergencies (Naser & Saleem, 2018). While, according to Fischer, Halibozek and Walters (2019), rescuers are trained in CPR and first aid and can offer emergency medical treatment to those in need. Rescuers are knowledgeable about standard rescue procedures, such as search and rescue efforts, evacuation techniques, and the appropriate use of rescue tools for they have attended trainings that are necessary for their field of work. Furthermore, Muñoz et. al (2020) stated that communication skills allow people to work in unison with emergency services and offer comfort and assistance to people in need. Hence, rescuers demonstrate quick and effective response skills due to their significant training and expertise, assuring the safety and health of individuals in need of help. Lastly, Ajzen (1991) explains that their ability to improve and continuously equip themselves with knowledge can be associated with the planned behavior theory, in which the plan and intention are connected to produce a positive behavior.

Conclusions

The main objective of this research is to unveil the lived experiences faced by the rescuers. Attaining the goal includes determining the challenging experiences of the rescuers, exploring the coping mechanisms of the rescuers, and identifying the insights of rescuers when faced with challenges.

Upon analysis, it was determined from the responses of the participants, rescuers often had difficulties having resources and enough manpower as they continue to respond to rescue operations. Rescuers faced risky and dangerous situations given the field and job that they have. Despite their intentions to help, rescuers experience harassment and being mocked which have been part of the challenges and struggles they faced as a rescuer.

As researchers evaluate the coping mechanisms of rescuers, the results and analysis cast light on a number of significant findings. In the study, rescuers adopted a variety of coping mechanisms to effectively manage the challenges and stressors associated with their roles. The rescuers relied primarily on social support networks, such as their coworkers and supervisors, for emotional and informational support. In addition, self-care activities and recreational activities played an important role in their coping process. The rescuers also demonstrated resilience and a sense of purpose as a result of their commitment to their job and the positive impact they had on those whose lives they saved.

Rescuers have learned significant lessons from their experiences. They get heightened situational awareness, remain composed in stressful situations, and effectively communicate with their team and people in need. They can handle uncertain events due to their flexibility and problem-solving abilities, and those they help will be taken care of emotionally due to their compassion and empathy. In order to effectively carry out rescue operations, rescuers must possess a special combination of skills: vigilance, composure, communication skills, adaptability, and compassion.

Overall, the findings highlight the significance of nurturing supportive environments, promoting self-care practices, and fostering a sense of purpose among rescuers in order to make light of their experiences, improve their coping mechanisms, and reflect on the insights as they go through challenges.

Implications

The main objective of this study is to explore the lived experiences of Davao rescuers during rescue operations, it is important that their experiences including challenges and struggles, coping mechanisms when facing challenges, and insight throughout their services must be taken into account to fully understand them. The results also indicate the need for resources given that they lack most of them including manpower during tough times. Additionally, this shed light on potential avenues for support and interventions that can significantly benefit rescuers in managing and overcoming these challenges. It is also best to create a much better coping mechanism for rescuers and give them support psychologically as they continue to go through traumatic events. As mental health advocates, it is best to help them by offering psychological first aid and giving them the assurance that there are people that can help when dealing with their current situations.

Moreover, their participation in this study has greatly helped the researchers understand that hardships are encountered by the rescuers all throughout their rescue operations and are still often criticized, despite their efforts. Following the proper procedures during rescue operations, ensuring everyone's safety all the time, and considering teamwork, cooperation and proper handling of circumstances are what helped the rescuers continuously do their job even though it was tough. The rescuer's passion to serve is also one of the things that kept them going. Hence, the rescuers' presence of mind before, during, and after the rescue operations greatly contributed to successful operations. The rescuer's ability to cope despite hardships is unbreakable as well. Injuries are mostly unavoidable but when passion comes with it, everything becomes bearable for the rescuers. Consequently, the findings provide a comprehensive understanding of the strategies employed, including maintaining a positive mindset, seeking support from others, and other activities. These findings are crucial in recognizing how rescuers persist despite their difficulties and highlight the importance of identifying effective coping strategies to address their challenges.

Furthermore, it is recommended that the government give focus and enough resources to the needs of rescuers given that they conduct rescue operations to save lives. Psychological assistance must also be given priority for each and every rescuer. Students and future researchers may utilize this study as a basis for future research and may include their study of other first responders such as volunteer organizations, emergency medical services, fire departments, and police services. They may discover additional factors related not just to the rescuers' personal experiences in the future. Lastly, it is best to give focus on other motivating factors such as benefits, salary, passion, and willingness of the rescuers that keeps them going and how it impacts their performance.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Maejan Bilao

University of Mindanao – Philippines

Rose Eden Dagohoy

University of Mindanao – Philippines

Kriziella Alexandra Elman

University of Mindanao – Philippines

Silvino Josol Jr.

University of Mindanao – Philippines